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RIGHT TO PROTECTION AGAINST UNFAIR DISMISSAL AND OBSTACLES FOR ITS EFFECTIVE EXERCISE IN TIMES OF CRISIS

Abstract:

The right to protection against unfair dismissal is one of the fundamental rights of employees. It means that an employer cannot dismiss an employee unless there is a valid reason related to the capacity or conduct of that employee or to the employer's requirements. At the very core of this rule lies an inclination to create a balance between the need to protect employees, as the weaker (economically dependent and legally subordinate) party to the employment relationship, and the need to preserve employers autonomy in matters that affect their business activities.

In times of crisis, broad guarantees of employment security are criticized as an obstacle to overcoming the difficulties employers face in the market. On the other hand, the legal systems that give employers absolute freedom to dismiss employees are also criticized, because employees feel a bigger need for protection when they're facing the risk of (long-term) unemployment. These were the ongoing debates after the flare-up of economic crisis in the autumn of 2008, and certain European countries decided to loosen up the protection against dismissal (simplifying the dismissal procedures, shortening the notice period, decreasing protection against unlawful dismissal). However, there is fear that such solutions may not be able to induce increase in employment rates and that they may lead to a deeper social inequality and marginalization of the most vulnerable categories of workers. Therefore, this paper starts with the examination of the right to protection against unfair dismissal and its place in the corpus of labour rights, as well as the development and contemporary interpretations of the concept of valid reasons for dismissal. After that, the key aspects of the reformed rules on dismissal in European countries are identified, as well as the fundamental challenges and obstacles for effective exercise of the right to protection against unfair dismissal in Serbian legislation and practice. And in the end, we draw a conclusion that economic crisis can be a legitimate reason for amending the rules on dismissal, but that these amendments should not result in excessive insecurity of employees and violation of their fundamental social rights.

Keywords: *labour rights; reasons for dismissal; economic crisis; labour law reform; Republic of Serbia.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

For the vast majority of employees, working for an employer represents, for them and their families, a sole or a main means of subsistence. Termination of employment, therefore, represents an especially difficult event, not only in their professional lives (due to the loss of employee status and all the associated rights), but in their personal lives as well, since they are facing a decline in the standard of living as well as the disruption of their social status. Bearing all this in mind, as well as the inequality between the contracting parties (i.e. economic dependency and legal subordination of employees), one of the fundamental rules of contemporary labour law states that an employer may not dismiss an employee unless there are valid reasons for dismissal, such as employee's competence or conduct or employer's requirements.

Consequences of dismissal are particularly hard in times of economic and financial crisis. These changes often force governments to face cost cutting and mass unemployment issues, and employers to face the challenges of preserving business continuity, restructuring as well as collective redundancies.¹ This is why some experts criticize broad guarantees of employment security and see them as an obstacle to overcoming the difficulties employers face in the market. And that's why, at the beginning of the millennium, flexible regulation of dismissal was introduced, which was based on the view that the high costs of *open-ended employment contracts*, and termination of such contracts (severance pay, termination notice, dismissal procedure etc.) not only discourage employers from establishing a *standard employment relationship*, but encourage them to resort to *bogus self-employment*, as well as *undeclared work*.²

Flexible regulation of dismissal was promoted shortly after the start of economic crisis in 2008, especially in Greece, Italy, Portugal and Spain, as well as Estonia, France, Great Britain, Romania, Slovenia and Holland.³ The same goes for the Republic of Serbia, considering that flexibilisation has become one of the fundamental goals of the Serbian labour legislation, in accordance with the belief that it could decidedly increase foreign investment as well as the number of jobs. However, implementation of such labour reforms is associated with a significant risk of violation of fundamental labour rights, including the right to protection against unfair dismissal. Dismissal, in fact, represents one of the institutes of labour law where (non)existence of adequate protection of employees and employer arbitrariness is very noticeable, because employers often, by trying hard to cut

¹ European Network of Legal Experts, *Protection, Involvement and Adaptation. European Labour Law in Time of Crisis, Restructuring and Transition*, 2010, p. 1, <http://www.labourlawnetwork.eu>, (accessed 14 July 2015).

² I. Schömann, *Labour Law Reforms in Europe: Adjusting Employment Protection Legislation for the Worse?*, Brussels, European Trade Union Institute, 2014, p. 7.

³ Schömann, p. 5.

labour costs, end up having more power over employees than what they are entitled to under law. That's why the following words of Simone Weil sound just as plausible today as the day they were written in 1934: „Work is no longer done with the proud consciousness that one is being useful, but with the humiliating and agonizing feeling of enjoying a privilege bestowed by a temporary stroke of fortune, a privilege from which one excludes several human beings by the mere fact that one enjoys, in short, a job”⁴

Still, we should critically re-examine the views that claim there is a strong relationship between strict rules on protection against dismissal and increasing (direct and indirect) costs, since some research shows that rules on protection against unfair dismissal don't necessarily burden employers with unreasonable costs. Besides, one shouldn't lose sight of the fact that flexible solutions, in many countries, resulted in impoverishment and marginalization of vulnerable categories of workers instead of creating new jobs. Therefore, we can legitimately ask if, and to which extent, can economic crisis represent a legitimate reason to lower the protection against unfair dismissal?

II. RIGHT TO PROTECTION AGAINST UNFAIR DISMISSAL AND ITS PLACE IN THE CORPUS OF LABOUR RIGHTS

The history of human rights law is inseparable from the realm of employment and employment relationships. Mostly because one of the major objectives of the „second generation“ human rights was the recognition of the fundamental rights and freedoms of employees as such in constitutions and international instruments for protection of human rights, including the right to work and the right to protection against unfair dismissal. Many authors, without hesitation, qualify labour rights as human rights, while some authors refrain from such qualifications or express doubts regarding its justification, believing that it is not enough that the labour rights are recognized as human rights in many international instruments for protection of human rights.⁵ These differing opinions, in fact, reflect the “old” dispute about the legal nature of economic and social rights and the idea of the necessity of drawing sharp lines of demarcation between this group of rights, on the one hand, and civil and political rights, on the other hand. However, drawing sharp boundaries between the two types of rights is considered unacceptable today, especially since the right to work means that everyone is entitled to earn a living from a freely chosen or accepted employment, and that everyone has the opportunity to develop their own

⁴ S. Weil, *'Reflections Concerning the Causes of Liberty and Social Oppression'*, in: *Oppression and Liberty*, trans. A. Wills and J. Petrie, London/New York, Routledge, 2004, pp. 36-37.

⁵ V. Mantouvalou, *'Are Labour Rights Human Rights?'*, *UCL Labour Rights Institute On-Line Working Papers*, vol. X, 2012, p. 1.

personality.⁶ Effective exercise of this right does not only contribute to the „survival of the individual and to that of his/her family, but insofar as work is freely chosen or accepted, to his/her development and recognition within the community“.⁷ The right to work, therefore, represents an „inseparable and inherent part of human dignity“, as well as the prerequisite to effective exercise of several other human rights, such as the right to life, health, housing and education.

Guaranteeing the right to work is not, however, an absolute and unconditional right of everyone to gain employment. Instead, it is centred on free choice or free acceptance of a job, as well as protection against unfair dismissal.⁸ It should be noted that in some states, legal guarantees of the right to work are primarily centred on employment security and protection of workers against unfair dismissal, while employment measures come in second. However, most contemporary authors, and the same goes for bodies responsible for monitoring the implementation of international instruments for protection of human rights, give priority to measures for ensuring equal opportunity for employment and free employment services – in comparison to measures aimed at protecting employment.⁹

In most European countries, employment security includes three elements: the first one being the rule that *no one can be dismissed without a justified reason*.¹⁰ Besides that, employment security also includes *appropriate financial compensation for dismissed employee*, as well as *procedural guarantees and appropriate sanctions for unlawful dismissal*, i.e. employees have the right to appeal against dismissal to an impartial body that will, in case of unlawful dismissal, award damages or reinstatement.¹¹ We should also bear in mind that protection against unfair dismissal has another important purpose, in addition to providing the employees with an opportunity to keep their employment on the basis of which they make a living. It represents a *specific guarantee for realization of other employees rights*, because there is a risk that employees, who fear for their jobs, may be reluctant to ask their employers to create the conditions for effective exercise of certain employment rights, such as the right to have *limited working hours*, safe and healthy working environment and fair wages. In this sense, we can conclude that the rules that guarantee

⁶ A. Cieslar, A. Nayer and B. Smeesters, *Le droit à l'épanouissement de l'être humain au travail: Métamorphoses du droit social*, Bruxelles, Bruylant, 2007, p. 126.

⁷ Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, *The right to work: General comment No. 18*, adopted on 24 November 2005, UN Doc E/C.12/GC/18, paragraph 1.

⁸ Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, paragraph 4.

⁹ L. Samuel, *Droits sociaux fondamentaux - Jurisprudence de la Charte sociale européenne*, 2^e édition, Strasbourg, Editions du Conseil de l'Europe, 2002, p. 13.

¹⁰ C. Kollonay-Lehoczky, 'Une „troisième voie“ en droit du travail? Un panorama du nouveau Code du travail hongrois: Entre un libéralisme extrême et des réminiscences de l'économie planifiée centralisée', *Revue de droit comparé du travail et de la sécurité sociale*, no. 2, 2012, pp. 86-87.

¹¹ Kollonay-Lehoczky, pp. 86-87.

a certain level of employment security, such as the rules on justified reasons for dismissal, may be essential for the effective exercise of labour rights.¹² This is the reason why stability of employment cannot be reduced to the protection of income of employees. Especially because contemporary labour policies have the tendency to lower the protection provided under the unemployment insurance system and to redirect the problem of unemployment towards the integration measures of the unemployed into the labour market. This turning point was inspired by the idea of the greater individual responsibility for protection against social risks as well as the belief that the generous system of unemployment insurance, rather than to stimulate the unemployed to seek out work, develops a culture of dependency to social benefits. This is why many legislators established the obligation of the unemployed to actively seek out and accept employment offered to them by the employment agency, or otherwise lose their right to unemployment benefits. Such draconian solutions, however, require special attention, especially when consequences, if the unemployed refuse unsuitable employment offered to them by the employment agency, are the same. This solution, as the European Committee of Social Rights concludes, can be qualified as „work which is exacted under the menace of any penalty“, in terms of the generally accepted definitions of forced labour.¹³ One of the objectives of unemployment insurance is to, at least in the initial unemployment period, protect the unemployed from the obligation to accept any employment and to enable them to find a job suited to their competence and skills. That was also the reasoning of the ILO Committee of Experts on the Application of Conventions and Recommendations, who pointed out that unemployment insurance rights are exercised only when the unemployed fulfil certain conditions regarding the minimum insurance period (prior payments of insurance contributions over a certain period of time), i.e. if the period of exercise of a certain right is determined based on the length of insurance period or period of employment, which is why imposing a new, additional requirement, that would involve having an (unsuitable) job, in order to exercise that right - represents mandatory labour under the threat of loss of the acquired social insurance right.¹⁴

¹² V. de Stefano, 'A Tale of Oversimplification and Deregulation: The Mainstream Approach to Labour Market Segmentation and Recent Responses to the Crisis in European Countries', *Industrial Law Journal*, vol. 43, no. 3, 2014, p. 281.

¹³ L. Samuel, *Droits sociaux fondamentaux*, p. 20.

¹⁴ Committee of Experts on the Application of Conventions and Recommendations, *General survey concerning the Forced Labour Convention, 1930 (No. 29), and the Abolition of Forced Labour Convention, 1957 (No. 105)*, paragraph 129. This view is important for the Serbian labour legislation, since the provisions of the *Law on employment and unemployment insurance* (Official Gazette RS, no. 71/03 and 84/04) stated that the unemployed shall be deleted from the records of the National Employment Agency in case they do not accept suitable employment that is offered to them, and that after nine months of unemployment – any job offered shall be considered suitable employment. The procedure was initiated to assess the constitutionality of this Law, since declining any job offer would lead to deletion from the Agency records, i.e. suspension of payment of unemployment benefits and the loss of health insurance, which can rightfully be qualified as punishment in relation to the provisions of the ILO Convention No. 29 concerning Forced or

III DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPT OF JUSTIFIED REASONS FOR DISMISSAL

Open ended employment relationship can be terminated at the initiative of either party. For employees, there are requirements regarding timely notice and prohibition of resignation at inopportune times, while limitations for the employers' right to dismissal do not only refer to the notice period and the dismissal procedure, but also to the reasons for dismissal. This is because employees earn their exclusive or predominant means of subsistence by working for an employer, and by entering into an employment contract, they take on the obligation of working in the name of, on behalf of and under the (managerial, normative and disciplinary) prerogatives of the employer. This further means that, besides the actual power manifested in economic dominance, the employer also has prerogatives to organize, direct and control the work of employees, lay down the rights, duties and responsibilities, as well as punish them for breach of work obligations. Without these prerogatives, effective organization of employer's activities would not be possible, which is why the employer's right to unilaterally terminate employment relationship is an important complement to the aforementioned prerogatives.

The first legal interventions concerning termination of employment relationship entailed the confirmation of freedom of employer and employee to unilaterally terminate open ended employment contract for any reason at all, with restrictions related to the notice period and severance pay rules. Legal rules however couldn't ensure the full protection of the weaker party to the employment relationship, because an employer could, at any time (and without any consequences), relegate the business risk to his employees. That's why, at the later stages of labour law development, employers were, in certain cases, forbidden from firing their employees or restricted in doing so.

Each legal system defines the circumstances under which an employer may terminate employment relationship. Although comparative law recognizes exceptions that are based on the ideas of the employment at will doctrine, which includes the right of the employer to fire an employee no matter what the reason, the contemporary labour law has mostly abandoned or modified the general rules of the obligation law regarding termination of contract.¹⁵ That included the development of several institutes of labour law, starting with the principle that an employer cannot terminate a contract *ad nutum*, but rather only for

Compulsory Labour. Luckily, the new *Law on employment and unemployment insurance* (Official Gazette RS, no. 36/09 and 88/10) abandoned this solution and defined the suitable employment, in the first 12 months since the registration, as employment within the acquired level and type of education, and after this period as „employment at lower levels within the same or similar type of acquired education, in accordance with the individual employment plan, taking into account the experience and the current state of the labour market“ (art. 32-33).

¹⁵ B. Lubarda, *Radno pravo – Rasprava o dostojanstvu na radu i socijalnom dijalogu*, Belgrade, Pravni fakultet Univerziteta u Beogradu, 2012, pp. 718-719.

legitimate reasons. First limitations to the employers' right to dismiss were set in the Mexican Constitution in 1917,¹⁶ and later on in the provisions of the German Works Council Law from 1920, The Labour Law of the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic from 1922, The Norwegian Working Environment Law from 1936, as well as the Cuban labour legislation between 1934 and 1938.¹⁷ In 1920, The Weimar Republic was the first European country to introduce, although shyly, protection of employees against unfair dismissal, and 31 years later the Law on Protection against Dismissal was adopted, confirming that the social justification of a dismissal is the fundamental criterion of its legality. Solutions from the aforementioned Law also served as an inspiration and a template for many legislators. In fact, German legislation, especially the Law from 1951, heavily influenced the adoption of the standards of the International Labour Organization (ILO) concerning termination of employment at the initiative of the employer.¹⁸

From the historical perspective and the perspective of comparative law, protection against unfair dismissal included two approaches: the first approach included a general guarantee that employees will not be unfairly dismissed, i.e. that they will not be dismissed in a manner or under circumstances that are not „socially justifiable“ or can lead to abuse of employer's powers. The second approach included establishing the list of reasons when dismissal would be considered (i)llegal. The two approaches were „reconciled“ after the development of the concept of valid reasons for dismissal, under the auspices of the ILO. The foundation of this concept was set in the ILO Recommendation No. 119 concerning Termination of Employment at the Initiative of the Employer, which was based on two essential ideas of employment protection: a) the idea of protecting workers from arbitrary and unjustified termination of employment; and b) the idea of protecting workers against the economic and social difficulties inherent in the loss of employment.¹⁹ Standards that deal with the reasons for termination of employment, the notice period and the right to an appeal as well as standards that deal with the protection of income and protection against downsizing were instrumental in bringing these ideas to fruition. This is because the ILO Recommendation, other than protecting the workers and their income, sought to protect the employer's prerogative to make decisions on matters that may affect the operation of the undertaking, and to protect the state interest of preserving the social peace. The main standard of the ILO Recommendation No. 119 was the rule specifying that an employee has the right to stay employed unless there is a valid reason for termination at the initia-

¹⁶ Constitución Política de los Estados Unidos Mexicanos (1917), article 123, A, XXI.

¹⁷ V. Vannes and L. Dear, *La rupture abusive du contrat de travail – Théorie et applications*, Bruxelles, Bruylant, 2010, p. 81.

¹⁸ S. Laleta, 'Prestanak ugovora o radu', PhD Thesis, University of Zagreb, 2011, p. 171.

¹⁹ International Labour Conference, 82nd Session 1995, *Protection against unjustified dismissal. General Survey on the Termination of Employment Convention (No. 158) and Recommendation (No. 166), 1982 - Report of the Committee of Experts on the Application of Conventions and Recommendations*, International Labour Office, Geneva, 1995, paragraph 3.

tive of the employer. Although the provisions of the Recommendation confirm that valid reasons for dismissal may refer to the „capacity or conduct of the worker or operational requirements of the undertaking, establishment or service“, ILO failed to specify these three general categories of reasons. Instead, it was left up to member states to make a catalogue of valid reasons, in accordance with the national circumstances.²⁰

In spite of its legally non binding nature, or maybe because of it, the standards from Recommendation No. 119 had a significant role in improving employment security and legal protection from dismissal in ILO member states.²¹ Despite being well accepted, there was still a need to make the standards more clear and contemporary. That's why Convention No. 158 and Recommendation No. 166 were adopted in 1982, and today are considered a reliable base for defining the terms justified and unjustified dismissal. Provisions of Convention No. 158 reaffirm the rule that „the employment of a worker shall not be terminated unless there is a valid reason for such termination connected with the capacity or conduct of the worker or based on the operational requirements of the undertaking, establishment or service“.²² On the other hand, the catalogue of invalid reasons for termination of employment largely fits the list given in Recommendation No. 119, although authors of the Convention took the opportunity to amend it and make it more precise.²³

The presented solutions show that the International Labour Conference sought, through its norms, to point out the differences between unlawful and unfair termination of employment relationship. At the same time, ILO member states regulate justified and unjustified reasons for dismissal *via* labour laws, while some states prohibit every unfair or abusive dismissal by law and give judges and arbiters the prerogative to specify in each case the content and the limitations of the prohibition.²⁴ In many states, introduction of

²⁰ Making of the catalogues was facilitated by the Recommendation No. 119 which contained indicative list of reasons that were not to be considered as valid reasons for termination of employment such as: union membership or participation in union activities; acting or having acted in the capacity of a workers' representative; the filing of a complaint or the participation in a proceeding against an employer involving alleged violation of laws or regulations; race, colour, sex, marital status, religion, political opinion, national extraction or social origin.

²¹ Although assessments of the impact of Recommendation No. 119 on the reform of rules regarding termination of employment in ILO member states aren't unanimous, authors agree that not all aspects of these reforms can be „attributed to“ Recommendation No. 119, but that its adoption was a strong incentive to make changes regarding termination of employment. B. Napier, 'Dismissals – The New I. L. O. Standards', *Industrial Law Journal*, vol. 12, no. 1, 1983, p. 17.

²² ILO Convention no. 158, article 4.

²³ Also, based on Recommendation No. 166 the catalogue of invalid reasons for dismissal was expanded to include leave of absence due to national service (military or civil) and old age. The latter should contribute to the elimination of age discrimination in the narrow sense (discrimination towards old people), because it should be considered within the boundaries of the national legislation and the practice of taking the old-age pension.

²⁴ R. Pešić, 'Prestanak radnog odnosa – Uporedno proučavanje zakonodavstva i prakse u vezi sa regulisanjem ove institucije u pojedinim zemljama sveta', *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta u Novom Sadu*, vol. 3, no. 3, 1969, p. 189.

strict legal rules regarding termination of employment is „crowned“ with constitutional guarantees of the principle of legality of dismissal.

IV PROTECTION AGAINST UNFAIR DISMISSAL IN TIMES OF ECONOMIC CRISIS

The effectiveness and comprehensiveness of the protection of employees against unfair dismissal, to a large extent, depends on the social and economic changes. These changes require constant consideration, especially in times of economic and financial crisis, considering that some authors are of the opinion that the application of rules on protection against dismissal may cause negative macroeconomic effects, and more precisely, create obstacles for employment, because the high (direct and indirect) cost of dismissals discourage employers from hiring new employees.²⁵ This persuaded some legislators, after the start of economic crisis in 2008, to change the rules on termination of employment, starting with the simplified dismissal procedure, a shortened notice period and decreasing protection of workers in cases of unlawful dismissal. Also, some countries, such as Germany, made this reform before the first signs of crisis.

Although the reform of labour legislation, in some countries, included certain improvements in protection against dismissal, particularly when it comes to the special protection of vulnerable categories of employees, in most countries, the rule changes included a reduced protection against dismissal. In many countries, instead of the expected increase in employment, implementation of the amended rules led to a deeper social inequality and significant disturbance in employment stability. Therefore, we can conclude that economic crisis can be a legitimate reason to amend labour legislation, but that the amendments shouldn't lead to excessive insecurity for workers and shouldn't violate their fundamental rights. Especially since labour rights has been significantly jeopardized in some countries (Italy, Hungary), due to the possibility to derogate *in peius* provisions of the general collective agreement (with certain limitations, of course) *via* the provisions of the collective agreement with the employer, thus making the collective bargaining into a means for protection of employers' interests.²⁶

²⁵ H. Räsänen, 'Recent Labour Market Developments – An Overview', in: *Reconciling Labour Flexibility with Social Cohesion – Ideas for Political Action*, Strasbourg, Council of Europe Publishing, 2006, p. 61; European Commission, *Towards Common Principles of Flexicurity: More and Better Jobs through Flexibility and Security. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions of 27 June 2007*, COM(2007) 359 final, p. 12.

²⁶ G. Loy, 'La réforme italienne: Entre le malentendu de la flexicurity et la tentation du contrat unique', *Revue de droit comparé de travail et de la sécurité sociale*, no. 2, 2012, p. 39; T. Gyulavári and N. Hós, 'The Road to Flexibility? Lessons From the New Hungarian Labour Code', *European Labour Law Journal*, vol. 3, no. 4, 2012, p. 257; Kollonay-Lehoczky, *Une „troisième voie“ en droit du travail*, p. 76.

4.1. Catalogue of justified reasons for dismissal

The latest reforms of labour legislation in many European countries didn't include any intervention in the catalogue of valid reasons for dismissal. Estonia is an exception, because in 2009, the rules on reasons for dismissal were amended to include an increased prerogative of employers to terminate employment.²⁷ Besides, changes were adopted in relation to the reasons for dismissal that stem from employers' requirements, since they are very sensitive to economic crisis. Although the main objective of the aforementioned rules is to eliminate or alleviate, as much as possible, the negative effects that company restructuring can have on employees, the latest reforms in several European countries speak to the contrary. They primarily redefined the criteria for collective redundancy in order to enable employers to easily adjust to market changes (e.g. Czech Republic, Great Britain, Portugal, Slovakia and Spain).²⁸

The Greek Law attracted the most attention within the research sample, since Greek legislator opted for extreme changes allowing almost absolute flexibility of rules on dismissal. Although the legality of dismissal in this legal system wasn't dependant on existence of valid reasons, in practice, the prerogative of most employers, and especially the ones with many employees, to dismiss was limited by sources of autonomous law, which regulated the dismissal procedure and reaffirmed the requirement for justified reasons for dismissal.²⁹ It was precisely those limitations of the employer's prerogatives that have been rescinded by the Law no. 4046/2012³⁰ as have been the rights of employees to a notice period and unemployment benefits (assuming employment was terminated in the first year of the standard employment contract). The reform of the Greek labour law included the changes of the strict rules regarding collective redundancies, which used to require the approval of the trade union or a state representative. The aforementioned rule is rarely used in practice and yet Law no. 3863/2010 changed the number of workers whose dismissal can be qualified as „collective redundancy“ because of the abuse of successive dismissal of smaller numbers of workers than the number qualified as redundancy.³¹ The Greek example has shown the dramatic impact of economic crisis on labour legislation, with „deconstruction of labour laws“ and abandonment of its fundamental values.³² These consequences are serious, especially because the social benefits aren't generous in Greece,

²⁷ R. Rebhahn, 'Significant Changes/Trends in Dismissal Law Since 2006', in: European Labour Law Network, *Protection Against Dismissal in Europe. Basic Features and Current Trends*, 2011, p. 53.

²⁸ S. Clauwaert and I. Schömann, *The Crisis and National Labour Law Reforms: A Mapping Exercise*, Brussels, European Trade Union Institute, ETUI aisbl, 2012, p. 12.

²⁹ C. Papadimitriou, 'Le droit du travail Grec face à la crise: Un passage dangereux vers une nouvelle physiologie juridique', *Revue de droit comparé de travail et de la sécurité sociale*, no. 2, 2012, p. 12.

³⁰ Papadimitriou, p. 12.

³¹ Papadimitriou, p. 12.

³² Papadimitriou, p. 16.

and the culture of social dialogue is underdeveloped, as well as active labour market policies and the practice of lifelong learning, without which there is no support for the development of the concept of flexicurity.

There is an example from the French Law, that we should pay special attention to, which was the subject of discussion by the ILO tripartite committee. The case in question was related to the rules on the new recruitment contracts (*contrat 'nouvelle embauche'*), regarding which the French confederation of trade unions *Force ouvrière* addressed the Committee. This new type of contract, which was introduced in the French legal system in 2005, can be entered into by the employers employing less than 20 people, who have the right to, contrary to the rules of the Labour Code, dismiss an employee *for any reason* during the initial two year period (the so called employment consolidation period /*consolidation de l'emploi*).³³ The ILO Committee report that was unanimously adopted by the Administrative Council, concluded that these rules represented a violation of the provisions of ILO Convention No. 158. This was because the Convention allowed for the derogation of the rules on protection against dismissal during the probationary or qualifying period, which had to be a reasonable period of time; which is not how one could qualify the initial two year period of the new recruitment contract, despite taking into account all relevant factors (the time required to gain the skills and experience necessary to perform the entrusted work; the general interest to encourage small employers to employ young workers; catalogue of rights available to employees upon termination of the contract of new recruitment, particularly in connection with finding alternative employment; and the possibility of judicial protection because an employer abused his power /discriminatory dismissal/).³⁴ The Committee, therefore, concluded that the period of so-called consolidation of employment does not constitute a qualifying period of reasonable duration, which is why in 2008, the French legislator abolished the contract of new recruitment, as an institute of the labour law.³⁵

The view taken by the European Court of Human Rights, regarding the British Employment Rights Act (1996), which allows employers to dismiss employees without explanation within the first 12 months of recruitment, however, differs from the view of the

³³ *Ordonnance n° 2005-893 du 2 août 2005 relative au contrat de travail „nouvelles embauches“*; JORF, n° 179, du 3 août 2005, p. 12689.

³⁴ Report of the Committee Set Up to Examine the Representation Alleging Non-Observance by France of the Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organise Convention, 1948 (No. 87), the Right to Organise and Collective Bargaining Convention, 1949 (No. 98), the Discrimination (Employment and Occupation) Convention, 1958 (No. 111) and the Termination of Employment Convention, 1982 (No. 158), made under article 24 of the ILO Constitution by the Confédération générale du travail – Force ouvrière, Geneva, November 2007, GB.300/20/6, paragraph 89.

³⁵ Contracts that have been entered into by that time and under that name have been automatically altered into open ended employment contracts to which all the provisions of the Labour Code shall be applied. *Loi n° 2008-596 du 25 juin 2008 portant modernisation du marché du travail*, JORF, n° 148, du 26 juin 2008, p. 10224, article 9.

ILO Committee. The Court concluded that a one year qualifying period was introduced because the „Government considered that the risks of unjustified involvement with tribunals in unfair dismissal cases and the cost of such involvement could deter employers from giving more people jobs. Thus, the purpose of the one-year qualifying period was to benefit the domestic economy by increasing labour demand“.³⁶ The Court also commented on the length of the qualifying period, concluding that a one-year period is long enough to enable the employer to determine if the employee is suitable or not for the job.³⁷ This conclusion was sufficient to determine that „it was in principle both reasonable and appropriate for the respondent State to bolster the domestic labour market by preventing new employees from bringing unfair dismissal claims“.³⁸

4.2. Notice period

The notice period allows the employer to find a new employee to supplant the one whose employment will be terminated or to reassign his duties, and also allows the employee to find new employment during this period. ILO standards have established that „a worker whose employment is to be terminated shall be entitled to a reasonable period of notice or compensation in lieu thereof, unless he is guilty of serious misconduct“.³⁹ A long notice period may represent a significant burden and cost for the employer, especially if the employee was dismissed due to lack of competence or failure to achieve results, or due to redundancy.⁴⁰ This is the main reason why some legislators recently resorted to shortening of the notice period (e.g. Bulgaria, Greece, Estonia, Lithuania, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain). On the other side, Greek Law number 3899/2010 abolished the right to a notice period (and severance pay) for employees whose open ended employment is terminated in the first year on the job, which is considered to be the *probationary period*.⁴¹ The aforementioned solution was rightly seen as the violation of the provisions of the European Social Charter, which guarantees „the right of all workers to a reasonable period of notice for termination of employment“, as an important element of the right to a fair

³⁶ European Court of Human Rights, Judgement in Case *Redfearn v. The United Kingdom*, of 6 November 2012 (Application no. 47335/06), paragraph 53.

³⁷ European Court of Human Rights, paragraph 53.

³⁸ European Court of Human Rights, paragraph 53. Especially because the rule of exclusion of employees, who have been working less than 12 months, from the circle of protected persons is derogated in case of a dismissal due to race, gender, religion and other characteristics of the employee which could constitute the basis for discrimination.

³⁹ ILO Convention No. 158, article 11.

⁴⁰ E. Korpić Horvat, 'Ali pravna ureditev varstva za primer brezposlenosti sledi ciljem prožne varnosti', *Delavci in delodajalci*, vol. 10, no. 2-3, 2010, p. 332.

⁴¹ *Law number 3899/2010 on urgent measures for the implementation of the assistance program of the Greek Economy*, 17 December 2010 (Νόμος 3899/2010, ΦΕΚ 212/τ. Α/17-12-2010).

remuneration.⁴² European Committee for Social Rights confirmed that the right to a reasonable period of notice belongs to *every* category of employees, including the ones with atypical employment, as well as the ones on probationary employment.⁴³ Therefore, The Committee found the explanation by the Greek Government that the problematic provisions were introduced into the legal system due to the „financial vortex threatening the survival of its country’s economy“ unacceptable, in spite of it being a temporary measure that was to be abolished as soon as the economic situation would allow; and because of the political and economic difficulties Greece was facing, it was impossible to determine the actual timeframe for that.⁴⁴

4.3. The dismissal procedure and legal consequences of unlawful termination

Apart from the changes to the notice period, many European countries made changes (i.e. simplifications) to the dismissal procedure. This particularly included alleviation of the employer’s obligation to inform and consult the employees regarding dismissal (e.g. in Greece, Hungary and Spain), elimination of the requirement to get approval on dismissal from the relevant state authority (e.g. in Latvia), as well as limiting the opportunities to initiate labour disputes regarding dismissal (in Great Britain).⁴⁵ In some countries, the consequences for violation of the dismissal procedure were changed, and the most important innovation was that such violation no longer represented the reason for annulment of the dismissal, as well as that the employer was (only) obliged to compensate the employee (e.g. in Portugal and Spain).⁴⁶ It should also be noted that the changes of dismissal rules in most European countries included the consequences for unlawful dismissal, especially regarding the rights of employees to ask for reinstatement. New solutions were based on the idea that the reinstatement impacts in a negative way the employers’ ability to adjust the number and structure of employees to the needs of the market. On the other hand, there are authors who believe that reinstatement is just a symbolic measure without actual

⁴² *European Social Charter* (European Treaty Series, No. 35), article 4, paragraph 4.

⁴³ „While it is legitimate for such concepts (concepts of probationary or trial periods – Lj. K.) to apply to enable employers to check that employees’ qualifications and, more generally, their conduct meet the requirements of the post they occupy, the concept should not be so broadly interpreted and the period it lasts should not be so long that guarantees concerning notice and severance pay are rendered ineffective“. European Committee of Social Rights, Decision on the merit, *General Federation of employees of the national electric power corporation (GENOP-DEI) and Confederation of Greek Civil Servants’ Trade Unions (ADEDY) v. Greece* (Complaint No. 65/2011), 23 May 2012, paragraph 26.

⁴⁴ Resolution CM/ResChS(2013)2 adopted by the Committee of Ministers on 5 February 2013 at the 1161st meeting of the Ministers’ Deputies (General Federation of employees of the National Electric Power Corporation /GENOP-DEI/ and Confederation of Greek Civil Servants’ Trade Unions /ADEDY/ against Greece, Complaint No. 65/2011), paragraph 12.

⁴⁵ Clauwaert and Schömann, *The Crisis and National Labour Law Reforms*, p. 12.

⁴⁶ Rebhahn, *Significant Changes/Trends in Dismissal Law Since 2006*, p. 52.

capacity to deter employers from dismissal and that it only „encourages“ them to abuse and circumvent the existing rules.⁴⁷ That’s why there has recently been a growing number of countries where compensation is the only instrument of protection against wrongful termination, save for some exceptional cases such as discriminatory dismissal (e.g. in Hungary, Italy and Spain).⁴⁸

V. CHALLENGES AND OBSTACLES FOR EFFECTIVE PROTECTION AGAINST UNFAIR DISMISSAL IN SERBIAN LEGISLATION AND LEGAL PRACTICE

In Serbian law, like most other legal systems, the process of limiting the employer’s right to terminate employment was gradual and long. The first state intervention in this field was undertaken in the first decades of the XX century, announcing a wave of interventionism that was powerful enough to engage all the important aspects of the protection of employees, with „dissolution“ of the rules of the obligation law, that were based on the principle of party autonomy and the principle of equality of the parties.⁴⁹ After World War II, a new context for further development of protection against dismissal consisted of the Yugoslav socialist self-management law, in which a completely new concept of employment was endorsed, because managerial and other prerogatives that traditionally belonged to the employer, now belonged to the workers. The highest standards of protection against dismissal were set by the Law on Mutual Relations of Employees in Associated Labour⁵⁰ and the Law on Associated Labour,⁵¹ which ruled out the possibility of dismissing an employee against his will or without establishing his guilt. These laws included a historically unique rule that employment cannot be terminated due to technological or

⁴⁷ M. Tiraboschi, ‘Italian Labour Law After the So-Called Monti-Fornero Reform (Law No. 92/2012); *E-Journal of International and Comparative Labour Studies*, vol. 1, no. 3-4, 2012, p. 84.

⁴⁸ Schömann, *Labour Law Reforms in Europe*, p. 32-34.

⁴⁹ The initial step towards the establishment of elementary social justice in the field of termination of employment has been made with the *Workshops Act* (Serbian Gazette, of 29 June 1910), which, in principle, gave both parties to the employment contract an equal freedom to terminate the contract, if they respected the notice period. *The Law on protection of workers* (Official Gazette of the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats and Slovenians no. 128/XXI, 75/XIV, 72/XXII and 135/LXII) and the new *Workshops Act* (Official Gazette of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, number 262/LXXXI) announced a new approach in regulating the termination of employment, which included a requirement that every dismissal be explained and motivated by valid reasons, distinguishing between legal and illegal, justified and unjustified reasons for dismissal. Provisions of these laws guaranteed a special protection from dismissal in favour of pregnant women, women who recently gave birth and workers’ representatives, as well as employees who participated in military exercises.

⁵⁰ Official Gazette SFRY, no. 22/73.

⁵¹ Official Gazette SFRY, no. 53/76, 57/83, 85/87, 6/88 and 38/88.

other advancements, which, in practice, often resulted in irrational employment policies and retention of employees even after the real need for them ended.

After decades of development within the framework of the self-management concept of employment relationship, labour legislation started to return, at the end of the 1980s, to the classic contractual concept of employment relationship.⁵² With each new law, effort was made to continue with consistent implementation of the contractual concept of employment relationship and to round out the concept of justified reasons for dismissal, whose norms were honed in the labour laws of 2001 and 2005.⁵³

In that sense, one of the fundamental rules of the current labour law of the Republic of Serbia reads: an employer may not dismiss an employee without a justified reason relating to employee's competence or conduct or employer's requirements. This rule was confirmed in the latest Amendment to the Labour Law⁵⁴, which was adopted with the aim to cut labour costs, increase foreign investment and stimulate employment, through flexible rules. This included new rules on dismissal, some of which improve and some of which limit the protection of employees⁵⁵. This was done despite the fact that, according to the World Bank and International Labour Organization, Serbian Labour Law, in terms of strictness of legal protection of employment, ranks „somewhere around the European and world average“.⁵⁶ Right up until 2014, the notice period in Serbia was between one and three months, but just like so many European countries, that period was shortened, in the last Amendment to the Labour Law, to 8 to 30 days. Also, legal consequences of unlawful dismissal have been changed, meaning that the court will reject an employee's request for reinstatement, if it finds that there were grounds for termination of employment, even though the employer acted contrary to the rules of the dismissal procedure.

⁵² More on the development of Serbian labour law in: Lj. Kovačević, 'Évolution du concept de la relation de travail dans le droit serbe: d'un concept autogestionnaire authentique à une (ré)affirmation tardive du concept contractuel', *Revue de droit comparé du travail et de la sécurité sociale*, no. 1, 2015, pp. 28-37.

⁵³ See: *Labour Law* (Official Gazette RS, no. 70/01 and 73/01); *Labour Law* (Official Gazette RS, no. 24/05, 61/05, 54/09, 32/13 and 75/14).

⁵⁴ *Amendment to the Labour Law* (Official Gazette RS, no. 75/14).

⁵⁵ Certain novelties that were introduced regarding termination of employment deserved praise, since they filled the gaps and eliminated the shortcomings that created serious problems in practice. This refers to specifying the reason for dismissal that consists of the breach of work obligation and labour discipline. Special protection during pregnancy, maternity leave and child care leave has been improved as well, considering that the contract of employment cannot be terminated in these situations, and that the limited term employment is extended until the leave expires. In addition, in the event of a dismissal that an employee feels is related to his work as the workers representative, his trade union membership or his participation in trade union activities, the burden of proof has been transferred to the employer to prove that the dismissal or placing an employee at a disadvantage was not the consequence of that status or those activities.

⁵⁶ M. Arandarenko, *Tržište rada u Srbiji. Trendovi, institucije, politike*, Belgrade, Centar za izdavačku delatnost Ekonomskog fakulteta u Beogradu, 2011, p. 178.

In this case, the employee is only protected by the right to a guaranteed compensation of up to six salaries.⁵⁷

There are instances of dismissal in Serbian law that haven't been sufficiently regulated, which can deprive certain legal guarantees of their legal content, and also separate them from the purpose for which they were established. In addition, it should be recognized that a considerable number of persons who fall within the scope of application of labour legislation are effectively denied the opportunity to enjoy protection against unfair dismissal, among other things, because employers, by trying to cut labour costs no matter what, often find ways to avoid implementation of rules on protection against dismissal. This is evidenced by numerous court cases on unlawful dismissal, which, together with the large number of laid-off employees, vividly shows that existence of solid legal rules on dismissal cannot ensure effective protection of employees against unfair dismissal.

5.1. Dismissal due to the lack of results or lack of competence

In accordance with the standards of ILO as well as the Serbian courts jurisprudence, in the last Amendment to the Serbian Labour Law, for an employer to dismiss an employee due to the lack of results or lack of competence, he will first have to notify an employee about the shortcomings in his performance, provide guidance and an appropriate deadline for him to improve performance, making the dismissal legal only if the employee doesn't improve his performance in the set deadline.⁵⁸ The legislator, however, failed to establish the principles of evaluation of competence and performance, which represents a serious risk to employment security. The aforementioned issues are rarely regulated through collective agreements, unilateral acts of the employer or employment contracts, which is why employers often arbitrarily select the methods and criteria for appraisal of performance and competence. This may result in the abuse of reasons for dismissal, which is why the Labour Law should have limited the employer's prerogatives regarding performance evaluation, by, at least requesting that the appraisal criteria used, match the purpose of appraisal and ensure an objective verification of performance. In addition to these material requirements, certain procedural guarantees should be determined, ranging from the employer's obligation to inform employees regarding the criteria and procedures for evaluation, to establishing the rules on prerogatives for evaluation. In addition, the Law should establish clear rules regarding consequences of evaluation, monitoring of evaluators and other guarantees in connection with the evaluation. Employers should refrain from using the evaluation methods that may endanger the mental health of em-

⁵⁷ *Labour Law* (Official Gazette RS, no. 24/05, 61/05, 54/09, 32/13 and 75/14), art. 191, para 7.

⁵⁸ *Labour Law* (Official Gazette RS, no. 24/05, 61/05, 54/09, 32/13 and 75/14), art. 180a. Cf.: ILO Recommendation No. 166 concerning Termination of Employment at the Initiative of the Employer, point 8; Judgement of the Serbian Supreme Court Rev. II 17/06, 29 March 2006, *Bilten sudske prakse*, no 3, 2006, pp. 77–78.

ployees, which is most obvious in methods that are focused exclusively on increasing the productivity of employees, consequently creating a virtually unlimited competition between them (e.g. ranking).⁵⁹

5.2. Dismissal due to employee conduct

Misconduct of employees can have significant consequences for their legal and employment status; it can create justified reasons for dismissal due to breach of work obligation, discipline or due to being found guilty in the court of law for a crime at work. The status of employees can be affected by their actions at the workplace and during the working hours, as well as their actions otherwise associated with the tasks performed for the employer. Employee's actions that are not related to work in the name, on the behalf of and under the prerogatives of the employer, cannot constitute a reason for termination of employment.⁶⁰ However, there are exceptional cases where „disciplinary immunity“ of facts from the private life of an employee may be revoked or restricted.⁶¹ To be more precise, these are the cases where a close connection between the facts from the private life of an employee and successful operation of the company exists, when the conduct of an employee is causing real disturbance in the company (financial loss, loss of clients, damage to the reputation, disruption of the relationship between colleagues that prevents or hinders the work of employees etc.), even if that is happening outside of working hours and the workplace.⁶² Serbian legislator did not regulate this issue, nor has the court practice developed. However, we can conclude that the cases in question are the ones where *the nature of work performed by an employee for the employer is closely connected with the facts he's been charged with*. In practice, however, it is quite delicate to qualify this as a justified reason for dismissal, due to legal uncertainty and the risk of qualifying as justified the conduct that is only indirectly and loosely, or even artificially, connected with the entrusted work.⁶³ This finally means that the absence of *unambiguous specific link between*

⁵⁹ A. Chirez, 'Notation et évaluation des salariés', *Droit ouvrier*, Août, 2003, p. 310.

⁶⁰ A. Cœuret and É. Fortis, *Droit pénal du travail*, 4^e édition, Paris, LexisNexis/Litec, 2008, p. 78.

⁶¹ J. Savatier, 'Porté de l'immunité disciplinaire du salarié pour les actes de sa vie personnelle: Cass. soc., 25 et 26 février 2003', *Droit social*, no. 6, 2003, p. 629.

⁶² This has been confirmed in the French case law in the form of a rule stating that the conduct of the employee that is causing real disturbance in the company (*trouble caractérisé au sein de l'entreprise*) may represent a cause for sanctions against the employee, even if it happened outside of working hours and the workplace (J.-E. Ray, 'Vies professionnelles et vies personnelles', *Droit social*, no. 1, 2004, p. 8). In line with this view is the decision number 4501/79 of the Serbian Court of Associated Labour which confirms that „the breach of work obligation can be caused outside of the workplace if the worker is damaging the reputation of the organization and thereby disturbing the company operations“. Acc. to D. Simonović, *Radnopravna čitanka. Druga knjiga*, Belgrade, Službeni glasnik, 2009, p. 33.

⁶³ C. Jacquélet, *La vie privée du salarié à l'épreuve des relations de travail*, Aix-en-Provence, Presses Universitaires d'Aix-Marseille, 2008, p. 253.

conduct and professional activities of an employee must be regarded as sufficient reason for the preservation of “disciplinary immunity” of the facts from the private life. Any other solution would mean that the employer is given excessive powers and that the rules on dismissal have turned against the weaker party to the employment relationship. In these cases, the requirements for implementation of rules regarding legal determination of breach of work obligation haven’t been met and prohibited actions from private lives of employees are determined arbitrarily as well as *ad hoc*. Related to this is the question of how to establish the rules employees have to adhere to, even in certain aspects of their private lives, for their conduct to be considered appropriate. Serbian theory and practice have yet to answer these questions, considering that right now they’re dealt with only as factual questions for each case individually and without a clear „template“.

On the other hand, the last thirteen years, Serbian legislator didn’t directly or completely regulate issues of disciplinary liability and did it only through the institute of dismissal. This unique nomotechnical and conceptual solution was interpreted differently. One group of authors held the position that the labour laws from 2001 and 2005 do not recognize disciplinary liability as a special kind of liability of employees, while another interpretation was based on the belief that social partners are allowed to use sources of autonomous law to set disciplinary procedure and sanctions. The Amendments to the Labour law from 2014 have „resolved“ this dilemma in favour of the position of disciplinary liability as a kind of legal liability of employees, by introducing fines and warnings before dismissal as new disciplinary measures. The latter is important in creating conditions for effective implementation of principle of *progressive sanctions*, as well as in providing employers the opportunity to impose different measures that may contribute to ensuring a good functioning of the company.⁶⁴

5.3. Dismissal due to employer’s requirements

In times of economic and financial crisis, vulnerability of the right to protection against unfair dismissal is most intensely manifested in the risk of circumventing the rules on collective dismissals. This risk includes the so called „intelligent fragmentation of workforce“, considering that certain employers are trying to circumvent their obligations that

⁶⁴ Although by regulating the disciplinary liability within the institute of dismissal, certain procedural guarantees are ensured for employees who are found liable for major disciplinary offences, we must not lose sight of the necessity to protect the fundamental rights of employees. Without it, it’s impossible to achieve even a formal equality between parties, considering that neither the breaches of work obligation, nor employee culpability can be presumed. Especially because the principles of just and fair procedure must be implemented when establishing disciplinary liability. This involves reaffirming employers’ obligation to inform employees about the rules of procedure, to create conditions for effective exercise of their rights to a defence as well as an appeal, and to establish short deadlines to initiate and conduct a disciplinary procedure and impose disciplinary measures. In addition, there is a need to determine, through sources of the autonomous law, the purpose for the money generated by fines, which should be primarily connected to improvement of working conditions.

stem from relevant rules by dismissing the workforce little by little i.e. by dismissing the number of employees that is smaller than the number qualified as redundancy, that can gradually lead to the shutting down of the company. In addition, the practice in Serbia shows that the rules on collective dismissals can be circumvented by reducing the number of employees by offering them to enter into a mutual agreement on termination of employment, with the so called stimulating severance pay.

Dismissal due to rejection of an employer's offer to change the essential elements of the employment contract because of operational or organizational requirements also carries the risk of abuse. We should also keep in mind that the right to reject an employer's offer to change the employment contract is the absolute right of an employee, which he can exercise even if the proposed changes are minimal or more favourable to him. Therefore, an employer who, in spite of an employee's refusal to accept the offer to conclude the annex, *via facti* imposes the modification of the employment contract, will be in breach of the contract. If the conditions of the contract are unilaterally altered, the employee is not obliged to perform the new tasks, work at a new workplace or under any new conditions.

Termination of employment due to rejection of an employer's offer to conclude an annex to the employment contract will be null and void if it was done with discriminatory motives. In Serbia, this risk is particularly pronounced in relation to employees who use pregnancy and maternity leave, since there is a risk of transfer to a lower level job upon their return from leave, as well as a risk that exercising these rights may lead to the loss or limitation of rights and benefits related to the working conditions, particularly wage.⁶⁵ Such transfers can cause discrimination, and can be misused in a number of ways, e.g. a calculated transfer to a job that is about to be eliminated or a proposed transfer in order to harass an employee or place him in less favourable working conditions. The risk of abusing the transfer becomes that much more serious if we keep in mind that employees are faced with economic pressure to accept the employer's offer to amend their employment contracts, because the alternative is the loss of a job and the risk of long-term unemployment.⁶⁶

5.4. The circle of protected persons

A particular problem in the application of legal rules for dismissal in the Republic of Serbia is the fact that a considerable number of persons who fall within the scope of la-

⁶⁵ Despite the fact that Serbia ratified the UN and ILO conventions that guarantee special protection of workers during pregnancy and maternity: Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (art. 11, para. 2, point b); ILO Convention No. 156 concerning Equal Opportunities and Equal Treatment for Men and Women Workers: Workers with Family Responsibilities (art. 7); ILO Convention No. 183 concerning the revision of the Maternity Protection Convention (Revised), art. 8, para. 2.

⁶⁶ J. Rivero and J. Savatier, *Droit du travail*, Paris, PUF, 1956, p. 330. As well as A. Martinon, *Essai sur la stabilité du contrat de travail à durée indéterminée*, Paris, Dalloz, 2005, pp. 132-133.

bour legislation are *in effect* denied from enjoying the protection against unfair dismissal. This is because employers, by trying to cut labour costs no matter what, often have a much higher true impact on employees than what they are entitled to under laws. At the same time, we should bear in mind that in practice, legal protection against unfair dismissal is gradually shrinking thanks to the *increase of limited term employment contracts*, as well as misuse of this type of contract, most notably by successively entering into the same type of contract by the same people for the same jobs, i.e. entering into such a contract even when it is not justified by the specific and temporary requirements of the employer or the employee. We can also add *production fragmentation* to the list, since the so called small employers are excluded from the scope of application of the rules on collective redundancies, while the position of employees in other dismissal cases becomes worse due to *the weakening of the role of the trade unions*, primarily because of the declining rates of unionization and union lack of agility in respect of ensuring the effective application of the labour legislation. This problem of non compliance and abuse of employers' powers cannot be solved only by changing the laws, but also by fortifying the inspections and other monitoring and protection mechanisms.

5.5. The impact of European integrations on protection against unfair dismissal

Efforts to harmonize Serbian legislation with EU law do not play a part in the strengthening of mechanisms for prevention of abuse of an employer's right to terminate employment. Mainly because *acquis communautaire* does not regulate termination of employment, even though the Treaty of Functioning of the European Union explicitly gives the power to EU institutions to regulate matters related to protection of employees in case of dismissal⁶⁷. However, European Parliament and European Council, to date, have not adopted the directive which would regulate key aspects of this delicate legal issue, especially valid reasons for termination, the (maximum and minimum) length of the notice period and the consequences of unlawful termination. The sensitivity of these issues, as well as the significant national differences in their regulation, are the reasons why we cannot expect this situation to change anytime soon. This is separate from the fact that the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union reaffirms the right of employees to protection against unfair dismissal⁶⁸ which reaffirms employment security as one of the values of the European Union legislation. This was confirmed in several directives that indirectly regulate termination of employment, as is the case with the directives governing non-discrimination in employment or limited term employment. At the same time, we should bear in mind that the directives on protection of rights of employees in cases of collective redundancies, transfer of undertakings and employer insolvency were adopted under the auspices of the European Economic Community. The first two of the three di-

⁶⁷ Article 153, paragraph 1, item d).

⁶⁸ Article 30.

rectives are significant for the application of the principle of employment security, even though their adoption, both in terms of the original text, but also in terms of their amendments, was not governed only by social, but also economic goals.

Because of all the obstacles that stand in the way of the minimal harmonization of rules on dismissal, the mere thought of harmonization of these rules is considered to be utopia. This, however, does not negate the possibility of applying certain *soft law* sources in this area, especially in the context of implementation of the „flexicurity“ concept, since it implies mitigation of strict rules on termination of employment and gives priority to the professional mobility of workers and their employment security in comparison to the job security. This is closely associated with the need to ensure employability of workers, i.e. to open up the possibility of being employed, even if it doesn't mean staying on the same job. Hence, there is room for the conclusion that the flexibility concept „opened the doors“ to deregulation of dismissal rules, which, based on the highly successful Danish model of flexicurity, should be accompanied by advanced measures of active employment policies and generous unemployment benefits.⁶⁹ Therefore, „Member States should assess and, where necessary, alter the level of flexibility provided in standard contracts in areas such as periods of notice, costs and procedures for individual or collective dismissal, or the definition of unfair dismissal“.⁷⁰ However, these views require critical re-examination because experience from several European countries shows that deregulation is not a satisfactory response to high unemployment.⁷¹

VI. CONCLUSION

In recent years, labour law, as never before, has been facing the pressure to gradually but inexorably alter its protective nature, in order to turn this branch of law into „an instrument for stimulation of enterprise competitiveness“.⁷² Especially because in public, flexible regulation and organization of work, as well as reduction of legal protection in order to cut labour costs and stimulate employment – are touted as instruments for overcoming economic and financial crisis. And yet, even the most consistent implementation

⁶⁹ F. Hendrickx, 'Flexicurity and the EU Approach to the Law on Dismissal', *Tilburg Law Review*, vol. 14, 2007-2008, pp. 103-104.

⁷⁰ *Jobs, Jobs, Jobs: Creating More Employment in Europe. Report of the Employment Taskforce*, November 2003, p. 28. Furthermore, it was concluded in the *Green Paper: Modernising labour law to meet the challenges of the 21st century* (COM/2006/0708 final), with regards to the view that providing certain aspects of protection of economically dependent workers was (un)justified, that „other rights, particularly those relating to notice and dismissal, tend to be restricted to regular employees having completed a prescribed period of continuous employment“.

⁷¹ Schömann, *Labour Law Reforms in Europe*, p. 13.

⁷² Loy, *La réforme italienne*, p. 48.

of these proposals in most European countries hasn't led to the creation of a significant number of good new jobs, but rather to the impoverishment of the population.⁷³ Labour law reforms undertaken for the purpose of deregulation of already flexible labour rules had an extremely negative impact on the fundamental social rights, deepened the inequalities among the population and strengthened their economic insecurities.⁷⁴ This trend has rightly caused a concern for many authors, especially if we take into account that „the assumption that the labour law reforms represent a way out of the crisis - is questionable”, just as „it is difficult to distinguish whether labour law reforms are a response to the economic crisis or merely accompany the crisis, with no certainty about any causal link between them“.⁷⁵

This conclusion is also true for the changes to the rules on termination of employment, although the reform of labour legislation, in several countries, included certain improvements in protection against dismissal, especially in the field of special protection of certain categories of workers. Still, in most countries, changes to the labour law included reductions in protection against dismissal and, especially, protection against unlawful termination (reducing the notice period, lowering the level of severance pay, changes to the rules relating to consequences of unlawful dismissal, particularly in relation to the right of an employee to request reinstatement). In most cases, implementation of the new solutions showed that they were *conceptually incorrect*, since some studies have already shown that the rules regarding justified dismissal don't necessarily burden employers with unreasonable costs,⁷⁶ and that the high employment rates can not be ensured only by reducing protection against dismissal. These findings are especially important for the countries that do not provide, through their social security system, sufficient protection for the unemployed. Besides, the countries whose employment agencies don't have the capacity to ensure the appropriate quality and scope of service to all interested persons, have shown restraint in decreasing protection from dismissal.

On the other hand, the mere existence of solid legal solutions isn't enough to ensure effective protection of employees from unfair dismissal, and it's very important that the labour laws are complied with. Without effective implementation, solid legislation does not have a value greater than „a dead letter“, which is often the case with rules regarding the dismissal procedure or rules on collective redundancy that are violated every step of

⁷³ Loy, p. 48.

⁷⁴ Clauwaert and Schömann, *The Crisis and National Labour Law Reforms*, p. 16.

⁷⁵ Clauwaert and Schömann, pp. 16-17.

⁷⁶ This was confirmed in the research that Ewing and Hendy conducted regarding the British law and practice, where they proved that the rules on justified dismissal do not burden the employers with excessive costs. Instead „it offers minimal protection for workers: too many are excluded from the legislation; it is too easy for an employer to justify a dismissal as not being 'unreasonable', and the remedies for those who are dismissed remain wholly inadequate“. K. D. Ewing and J. Hendy, 'Unfair Dismissal Law Changes - Unfair?', *Industrial Law Journal*, vol. 41, no. 1/2012, p. 121.

the way. Such state of affairs in practice does not mean, however, that these legal institutions lost their value or that they have become outdated. Instead there is a need to make them clearer and more certain and adaptable to the needs of society. Labour legislation, therefore, must be sensitive to changes occurring in the field of labour, must predict or at least identify and regulate them. This, however, cannot result in the betrayal of the idea of social justice and other ideas and values that express the spirit and the being of the labour law, including the requirement to respect the fundamental social rights. In that sense, European Committee of Social Rights has warned that the means by which social rights are unduly limited shouldn't be used for elimination of consequences of economic crisis.⁷⁷ This finally means that the economic crisis may constitute a legitimate reason for amending the existing laws and practices in order to limit public spending or mitigate the burden faced by the employers. However, the aforementioned amendments may not be achieved *via* excessive insecurity and destabilization of the status of subjects of fundamental social rights: „doing away with such guarantees would not only force employees to shoulder an excessively large share of the consequences of the crisis but also accept pro-cyclical effects liable to make the crisis worse and to increase the burden on welfare systems, particularly social assistance”.⁷⁸

⁷⁷ J.-P. Marguénaud and J. Mouly, 'La Comité européen des droits sociaux face au principe de non-régression en temps de crise économique,' *Droit social*, no. 4, 2013, p. 344.

⁷⁸ European Committee of Social Rights, paragraph 18.